

EFFECT OF SI CONTENT ON IMPACT-ABRASIVE WEAR RESISTANCE OF AL₂O₃P/STEEL COMPOSITES PREPARED BY SQUEEZE CASTING

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this work was to improve the impact-abrasive wear resistance of steel-based composites containing Al₂O₃ particulates (Al₂O₃p) through the use of squeeze casting and Si additions. In this case, Si powder ranging up to 25% of the Al₂O₃ content was added. Microstructures of the composites produced in this way were homogeneous in particle distribution and free from obvious defects. Composites were characterized by microscopy and with micro-indentation hardness tests of individual phases. The Si-free matrix contained only pearlite, but adding Si also produced ferrite. Impact-abrasion wear tests were performed using a hammer impacting on a rotating wheel that was flooded with quartz sand. The impact frequency was 80/min and the energy was of 2J. Adding Si obviously decreased the wear volume of the composites, and the minimum wear belonged to the 10% Si composite. The best wear-resistance can be attributed to two reasons: the relative higher hardness of the matrix and the strong interfacial bonding strength. The wear mechanism of the composites was abrasive wear when the Si content was less than 10%. At higher contents, it was a mixed mode of abrasive and delamination wear.

1 INTRODUCTION

As one of the commonest industrial problems, wear widely happens in mining, automotive, railroad and earth construction [1-3]. Nowadays, many studies have been focused on the development of wear-resistant materials, such as composite [4, 5], alloy steel [6, 7], and cemented carbide [8, 9]. Metal Matrix composites (MMCs), as a wear resistant material, are being increasingly used owing to their enhanced properties such as wear resistance combined with significant weight savings over unreinforced alloys. The commonly used metallic matrices include Al, Mg, Ti, Cu and their alloys [10, 11]. However, as is known to all, steel material cannot be replaced in engineering applications, especially the impact-abrasive wear conditions. Therefore, as the metallic matrix, steel material is vital to enhance wear resistance for Metal Matrix composites.

As metal matrix composites, steel based matrix composites reinforced with Al₂O₃ particulates (Al₂O₃p/steel composites) ideally combine the high hardness and wear resistance of Al₂O₃ ceramics with the ductility of steel metals, they show failure-tolerant behavior and therefore have the potential for a wide range of applications, especially the wear conditions [12-15]. However, at the present, the main limitations of Al₂O₃p/steel composites especially in wear related applications are their relatively low the strength and the hardness of the composites at room temperature. For example, S. Shamsuddin et al. [16] investigated a microhardness HV 80 for 25 weight percent Al₂O₃p/Fe-Cr steel composites. K. Lemster et al. [17] measured a bending strength 217 MPa for Al₂O₃p/X38CrMoV5-1 steel composites. This should be attributed to the weak interface bonding between Al₂O₃p and the steel matrix, because the wettability between pure Al₂O₃p and steel is very poor with a wetting angle of 150° [18, 19]. Therefore, the Al₂O₃p/steel composites often exhibit inferior wear-resistance, particularly in case of severe impact abrasive wear conditions. For example, in large ball mills, the liners made of Al₂O₃p/steel composite are easily dig out Al₂O₃p across the Al₂O₃p/steel interface due to the fact that abrasive particles intensely scratch and impact the liners.

In recent years, there have been some methods to improve the interfacial bonding strength in the $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{p}/\text{steel}$ composites. K. Lemster et al. [20] fabricated $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{p}/\text{steel}$ composites by pressureless infiltration method, in which $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{p}$ preforms contained 20 wt.% Ti powder were infiltrated by the steel liquid at 1600 °C for 24 h. E. Wang et al. [21] fabricated the Ni coating and the TiN coating on the surface of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{p}$ to improve the wettability between Al_2O_3 and the steel matrix. J. Feizabadi et al. [22] fabricated the nanostructure 304 stainless steel/ Al_2O_3 composite by using self-propagating high temperature synthesis process to improve the wear properties of the composites. N.Travitzky et al. [23] obtained the Al_2O_3 reinforcement through reaction infiltration to fabricate the $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{p}/\text{Fe-Cr-Ni}$ composites. However, problems still exist such as long fabrication period, low mechanical properties, high cost after all these research work. Therefore, it is urgent to seek efficient methods to improve the interfacial bonding and the mechanical properties for the $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{p}/\text{steel}$ composites.

In this present work, the wear properties of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{p}/\text{steel}$ composites were improved through the use of squeeze casting and Si additions. The impact abrasive wear performance of the composites with different Si content was investigated. The wear mechanism was proposed, and the wear behavior of the composites was analyzed.

2 EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

2.1 Materials

The experimental materials mainly included Si powder, $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{p}$ and 5140 steel (C 0.44 wt.%, Cr 1.00 wt.%, Mn 0.60 wt.%, Si 0.30 wt.%, and the balanced Fe). The $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{p}$ (from Saint-Gobain Ceramic Materials, Zhengzhou) were 99.75 weight percent in purity, 100~180 μm in size. Si powder was 99.5 wt.% in purity and 180~250 μm in size. The binder in the $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{p}$ preform was sodium silicate ($\text{Na}_2\text{O}\cdot n\text{SiO}_2$) solution, in which n was 2.5.

2.2 Fabrication of composites

In this work, the composites were fabricated by squeeze casting technology [24], which consisted of three steps. Firstly, the $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{p}$ preforms were prepared as follow. The $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{p}$, Si powder and the binder-sodium silicate solution were mixed in a ball mill for one hour. In this process, Si powder content was 5 wt.%, 10 wt.%, 15 wt.%, 20 wt.% and 25 wt.% of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{p}$'s mass, respectively and the binder-sodium silicate solution content was 3 wt.% of the total mass of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{p}$ and Si powder. Then the mixture was uniaxially pressed under 1MPa pressure to form the preform in a steel mold of 88 mm in diameter and 25 mm in height. Secondly, the demoulded preforms were heated up gradually from 20 °C to 850 °C at a heating rate of 5 °C /min, during which preforms were held for an hour at 350 °C. The heated preforms were placed rapidly at the bottom of a steel casting die which has a heat-insulation layer at the internal surface. Finally, the 5140 steel liquid infiltrated into the preforms to form the composites in the steel casting die by using squeeze casting. The squeeze casting process parameters included the pouring temperature 1580 °C, the pressing time after pouring 10~15s, the pressure 79.5 MPa, and the pressure holding time 40s.

2.3 Microstructure and micro-hardness test

The standard metallographic specimens of the composites were cut from the castings. Then a standard method consisting of grinding, mechanical polishing and etching with 4% nitric acid alcohol was used for metallographic analysis. A Leica EZ4D optical microscope (OM) was applied to observe the microstructure of the specimens. A HITACHI S-3400N scanning electron microscope (SEM) was used to observe the worn surfaces. The Image-Pro Plus software was applied to calculate the volume fraction of the $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{p}$ in the composites.

The Vickers hardness of the metal matrices in the composites was measured on polished samples using a micro-hardness tester (LEICAVMHT30M). The load was 200 g and the dwell time was 15s. Five micro-hardness values were measured for each matrix structure, and three of them were averaged after excluding maximum and minimum values.

2.4 The contact angle tests between steel containing Si and Al₂O₃p

To investigate the influence of the Si powder content in the preforms on the wettability, the contact angles between 5140 steel melt and Al₂O₃p were measured by the sessile drop method. Since only a few impurities in substrates can also affect the wetting, high purity Al₂O₃ substrates were used. The substrates had dimensions of 20 mm × 20 mm × 5 mm. The 3 mm × 3 mm × 3 mm 5140 steel specimens with different Si content were cut from the relative composites. Prior to measure the contact angles, those specimens were carefully cleaned in acetone with ultrasonic. The specimen was heated in a vacuum heating furnace. The contact angle was measured at 1873 K (1600 °C) in a vacuum of less than 1.8×10⁻³ Pa. The sessile drop was photographed with a camera. The coordinates of twenty points on the outline of the droplet were measured on projections of the monochrome negatives and the contact angles were calculated by using the Laplace equation.

2.5 Impact abrasive wear tests

The impact abrasive wear tests were carried out on a pin-on-ring typed MLD-10 wear tester (produced by Taihua Machinery Co., Ltd.) at room temperature, as shown in Fig. 1. The upper specimen was the tested composites with the size of 10 mm × 10 mm × 30 mm. The lower specimen was a ring of 50 mm in diameter and 15 mm in thickness, made of 5140 steel with a hardness of 57 HRC. The abrasives were quartz particles, whose hardness (800~1200 HV) was lower than that of Al₂O₃p (1800~2200 HV) in the composites. This ensured that the reinforcement particles could resist the wear of abrasive particles. In order to identify the difference in the impact resistance of the composites with different Si content, the impact energy was determined as 2J. Other parameters included the hammer's impact frequency 80 times/min, the rotation speed of the lower specimen 180 r/min, the linear speed of rotating friction wheel 0.47 m/s, and the flow rate of the abrasives 5 kg/min. All specimens were first worn for half an hour to eliminate the test errors from the surface contact between the ring and pin, then formal tests for two hours and a half. Before and after each test, the specimens were ultrasonic-cleaned in alcohol and weighted using an electric balance with a precision of 0.0001mg to obtain the mass loss. The mass loss of each composite was the average value of three specimens.

1-Dropping hammer; 2-Upper specimen 3-Lower specimen; 4-Quartz sand
Fig.1. Schematic diagram of MLD-10 tester

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Composites microstructure

Fig.2 shows the microstructure comparison of the composites without Si and with 15% Si, separately. There are some holes in the composite without Si (marked by circles in Fig. 2a), which are formed due to incomplete infiltration of the steel melt. However, there isn't any casting defect in the 15%Si composite, as shown in Fig.2 (c). Fig.2 (b) shows the matrix of the composite without Si consists of only pearlite. However, in Fig.2 (d), the matrix of the 15% Si composite is composed of black pearlite and white ferrite. Meanwhile, it is noteworthy that microstructure of the 15%Si composites is homogeneous in particle distribution.

Fig. 2. Microstructure of (a) the composite without Si (not etched) and (b) the composite without Si (etched), (c) the 15% Si composite (not etched) and (d) the 15% Si composite (etched), by OM

3.2 Influence of Si content on wear performance of composites

The volume losses, instead of the mass losses, were applied to characterize the impact abrasive wear performance of the composites. This is mainly because there is a difference between the steel and $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{p}$ in density. The volume loss of the composites was calculated as follow. Firstly, the mass losses were measured, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Mass loss of the composites

Si content / %	0	5	10	15	20	25
Mass loss / g	2.6924±0.02	2.3531±0.11	1.4230±0.16	1.7983±0.08	1.6934±0.23	1.8803±0.30

Subsequently, the density of the composites was calculated using the equation [25]:

$$\rho = \frac{m}{V} = \frac{1 \times V_1 \times \rho_1 + 1 \times V_2 \times \rho_2}{1} = V_1 \times \rho_1 + V_2 \times \rho_2 \quad (1)$$

Where V_1 is the volume fraction of the $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{p}$, ρ_1 is its density $3.98 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$, V_2 is the volume fraction of the 5140 steel matrix, ρ_2 is its density $7.47 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$. The volume fraction of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{p}$ was obtained according to measure the metallographic photo by using Image-Pro Plus 6.0 software. This method can ensure that the volume fraction is accurate and true. The result shows that the volume fraction of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{p}$ was 43.35%, 45.00%, 44.50%, 41.47%, 57.87% and 58.34%, respectively, as the Si content changed correspondingly from 0 wt.%, 5 wt.%, 10 wt.%, 15 wt.%, 20 wt.% to 25 wt.% of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{p}$. Moreover, M. R. Rosenberger et al. [26] in their investigations demonstrated that this theoretical density values match with the measured density values.

Finally, the volume losses of the composites were calculated by dividing mass loss with corresponding density. The result is shown in Table 2. Fig. 3 compares the volume losses of investigated composites. It shows that adding Si obviously decreased the wear volume of the composites. Fig. 3 also indicates that with the increase of Si content, the volume loss first decreased and then increased, reached the minimum wear at 10% Si composite.

Table 2 Volume loss of the composites

Si content/%	Density composite/g·cm ⁻³	of	Volume loss/cm ³
0	5.96		0.45±0.01
5	5.90		0.39±0.02
10	5.92		0.24±0.02
15	6.02		0.29±0.02
20	5.45		0.31±0.04
25	5.43		0.35±0.04

Fig.3. Relationship between volume loss and Si content

3.2.1 Influence of micro-hardness on wear performance of composites

Fig. 4 depicts the micro-hardness indentations of ferrite and pearlite in the steel matrix of the 20% Si composite. Fig. 5 shows the variation of Vickers hardness values of the metal matrix (ferrite, pearlite) with Si content. It is evident from Fig. 5 that the micro-hardness of the ferrite increased significantly when the Si content increased from 5% to 10%. This is mainly because the solid solution strengthening effect increased with the increasing Si content. However, when the Si content was above 10%, Si atoms started entering into pearlite. It gives rise to a decrease in the hardness of ferrite. As shown in Fig.5, when the Si content was above 15%, the hardness of pearlite decreased with the increasing Si content due to the increase of the volume fraction of the ferrite in the pearlite. In general, Si as an alloying element in steel, when added in small quantities, forms a solid solution with Fe, preferably ferrite [27]. Further, Calculating according to Fig. 6 shows that the volume fraction of ferrite in pearlite increased from 56.48%, 64.83% to 66.25%, as the Si content from 15 wt.%, 20 wt.% to 25 wt.%. This is attributed to the fact that the growth rate of the cementite in pearlite decreases due to the redistribution of Si between the cementite and ferrite [28].

It is well known that over the past decades, ferritic steels have not been widely used in applications requiring wear resistance. This could be contributed to the fact that the ferritic steels are relatively softer compared to other steels. However, the pearlite occurred in the soft ferritic matrix could improve hardness and abrasion resistance of steels matrix. Meanwhile, the abrasion resistance increased with the increasing volume fraction of pearlite [29]. Thus, the abrasion resistance mainly related to the hardness of pearlite. As mentioned above, when the Si content was higher than 10%, the volume fraction of ferrite in pearlite increased with the increasing Si content. This leads to the decrease of the pearlite hardness. For a soft matrix, large deformation and high density dislocations can be easily formed. Besides, a soft matrix could only bear low stress due to the low tensile strength.

It gives rise to the fact that the base material can be removed largely. Further, this result can be demonstrated by using the following formula [30]:

$$W_R = K \frac{P \varepsilon_{def}}{H \varepsilon_0} \quad (2)$$

Where W_R is the wear rate, H is the hardness, P is the applied load, ε_0 is the fracture strain of asperity, ε_{def} is the strain for asperity deformation and K is the wear coefficient. The above formula indicates that the wear rate of a material increases with decrease in hardness and fracture strain of the asperities. Thus, it is summarized that soft matrix would suffer more severe impact abrasive wear than hard matrix. It corresponds to the result of the wear experiments, as shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 4. Micro-hardness indentations in the matrix of 20%Si composite

Fig. 5. Relationship between microhardness of the metal matrix and Si content

Fig.6 SEM observation of the metal matrix: (a) 15%Si composite; (b) 20%Si composite; (c) 25%Si composite

3.2.2 Influence of the contact angle between Al₂O₃ and steel on wear performance of composites

The contact angles between 5140 steel melt with Si and Al₂O₃p were measured by the sessile drop method. The results show that the contact angle was 125°, 118°, 114°, 111°, 107° and 105°, respectively, as the Si content changed correspondingly from 0 wt.%, 5 wt.%, 10 wt.%, 15 wt.%, 20 wt.% to 25 wt.% of Al₂O₃p, as shown in Fig. 7. This means that the contact angle decreased with the increasing Si content. Recent investigations by Cheng Zhang et al. [31] revealed that the enhancement of the bonding strength results from the formation of the metallurgical bonding at the interface as well as complete wettability between the reinforcements and the matrix. In essence, the metallurgical bonding between particles and the matrix material has a significant affect on the mechanical behavior of composites [32]. From the 5%Si curve of Fig. 7, we can see that the contact angle decreased remarkably from 144 to 118 degrees within the first 114s after a full melting. Afterwards, the contact angle value was kept at a stable value of 118 degrees (see Fig. 8) up to a time of 786 s. In this process, the decrease of contact angle is mainly because there was a FeAl₂O₄ phase in the interfacial cross section between the metal matrix and the Al₂O₃ substrates [18]. Therefore, it leads to the formation of metallurgical bonding at the interface. Meanwhile, the formation of metallurgical bonding is believed to be a important sign for the enhancement of the bonding strength.

On the other hand, good wettability can help to conquer the capillary pressure at the interfaces and to avoid the formation of interfacial flaws; both contribute to the interfacial adhesion. The relationship between work of the adhesion (W_{ad}) and the contact angle (θ) can be expressed as [33]:

$$W_{ad} = \gamma_{LV}(1 + \cos \theta) \quad (3)$$

Where γ_{LV} is the surface tension of liquid-vapor phases. For a given solid surface, the solid-vapor γ_{LV} surface tension is expected to be constant. T. Laha [34] and R. E. Neuendorf [35] et al. presented a result that the lower the contact angle, the higher the work of adhesion and the better the bonding strength at the interface. Therefore, the Al₂O₃p/steel interfacial bonding strength and mechanical properties can be improved due to the decrease of the contact angle.

The wear behavior of particle reinforced composite depends on the type of interfacial bonding between the matrix and the particle reinforcement. When the Al₂O₃ particles are strongly bonded with the steel matrix, they protect the surface against sever destructive action of the abrasives. This is mainly because of the strong interfacial bond which plays a important role in transferring loads from

the matrix to the particles, resulting in less wear of the material [36]. The normal stresses generated at the poor interface easily exceed its bond strength [37]. It leads to the fact that in case of poor interfacial bonding, the interface offers site for crack nucleation and tends to pull out the particle from the wear surface. Therefore, the wear resistant of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{p}/\text{steel}$ can be improved due to the increase of interfacial bonding strength.

Fig. 7. The contact angles between the Al_2O_3 and the metal matrix with different Si content

Fig. 8. Photograph showing the wettability (contact angles) of 5140 steel droplet on the Al_2O_3 substrate at 1873 K

3.3 Worn surfaces and sub-surfaces

The surfaces of the composites after 150 min wear are shown in Fig. 9. The features of the worn surfaces include furrow, fragmented $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{p}$, press-in particulates, plastic deformation, and sub-surface crack. Fig. 9(a) shows an abraded surface of the composite without adding Si. There are many wide, deep and parallel grooves which should be formed by microcutting of the abrasive particles, a result of the impact force of the hammer and shear force of the rotating wheel forcing abrasive into the metal matrix. Besides, there are press-in SiO_2 particulates and broken $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{p}$ in the worn surface. The fragmentation of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{p}$ should be the result that brittle $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{p}$ were suffered to strong impact load. Fig. 9(b) shows the worn surface of the 5%Si composite. From Fig. 9(b), it can be also obviously observed that severe grooves are the main feature, and exposed $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{p}$ also can be seen in the worn surface. It indicates that the grooves were formed by microploughing [38] of the abrasive particles, and stopped by $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{p}$ reinforcements. Fig. 9(c) indicates 10%Si composite is not worn heavily,

because there are little and shallower grooves and more exposed $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{p}$ on the worn surface. Therefore, the wear mechanism is abrasive wear [39] when the Si content is less than 10%, and the wear volume decreases gradually with the increasing Si content.

Fig. 9. SEM observation of worn surface of the composites: (a) 0%Si, (b) 5%Si, (c) 10%Si, (d) 25%Si.

Fig. 9(d) shows the worn surface of the 25%Si composite. It indicates that there are furrows formed by microploughing on the worn surface, and many cracks are present around exposed $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{p}$. The wear mechanism of abrasive wear should be also present. Moreover, it is evident from Fig. 10 (a) that a greatly oxidized layer occurs in the worn sub-surface. Fig. 10 (b) and (c) show that there is a large amount of O element and Fe element in the oxidized layer. Fig. 11 shows that there is a plastically deformed layer under the oxidation layer. All these indicates that a greatly oxidized deformation layer is formed on the worn surface of the composite due to intense plastic flow of the sub-surface materials under impact abrasive wear [40]. However, this intense plastic flow could be hindered by the $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{p}$. Therefore, as shown in Fig. 12, microcrack nucleation occurs at the interface between $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{p}$ and matrix under the shear force of friction. Meanwhile, the cracks also propagate easily along the interface between the oxidization layer and below plastic deformation layer, as shown in Fig.11. The presence of the oxidization deformation layer and the cracks indicates that the wear mechanism of delamination exists for the 25% Si composite. Hence, the wear mechanism is a mixed mode of abrasive and delamination wear [41]. The schematic illustration of wear mechanism is shown in Fig. 13.

Fig. 10. the worn subsurface of 25%Si composite, (a) SEM image, (b) EDS of element O, (c) EDS of element Fe

Fig. 11. SEM image of the subsurface of 25%Si composite. Fig. 12. Cracks in subsurface of 25%Si composite

Fig. 13. The schematic illustration of delamination wear mechanism for the composites

3.4 Wear behavior of Al₂O₃p/steel composites

According to above analyses, the wear behavior of the composites can be described as follows:

The impact abrasive wear behavior of the Al₂O₃p/steel composites is likely controlled by a combination of the hardness of the metal matrix and the Al₂O₃p/steel interfacial bonding strength. As mentioned above, the wear mechanism is abrasive wear for the composites with Si less than 10%, so the dominant factors are the hardness of the metal matrix and the interfacial bonding strength. The composite without adding Si shows the lowest wear resistance, because the hardness of the matrix is the lowest which leads to its intense plastic flow, and the interfacial bonding strength is the weakest which causes spalling of Al₂O₃p from the matrix during wear. The wear behavior of the 5%Si composite is similar to the composite without Si. However, the 5%Si composite has the higher hardness of the metal matrix and interfacial bonding strength due to 5% Si adding. Therefore, the 5%Si composite has the higher wear resistance than the composite without Si.

The wear mechanism of the 10%Si composite is abrasive wear, and the dominant factors are the hardness of the metal matrix and the interfacial bonding strength. Besides, the volume fraction of Al₂O₃p can also affect the wear behavior of composites to some extent. In the wear experiment, the 10%Si composite exhibited best wear resistance. The reasons include three aspects. Firstly, its matrix has the highest hardness. Secondly, the stress triaxiality cannot be concentrated for the Al₂O₃p spacing in the 10%Si composite because the Al₂O₃p distributed uniformly in the matrix with the volume fraction about 44.5% [42]. Thirdly, the contact angle between the matrix and Al₂O₃p is lower than those composites with lower Si added, which indicates superior interfacial bonding. This gives rise to the fact that the reinforced hard Al₂O₃ particles protect the matrix surface against destructive action of the abrasive during wear process. Therefore, the grooves become shorter and shallower, because the grooves formed by microcutting are blocked by the exposed Al₂O₃p (see Fig.9(c)).

When the Si content is higher than 10%, the wear mechanism of the composites is a mixed mode of abrasive and delamination wear. In addition to the dominant factors, the degree of dispersion of Al₂O₃p also affects the wear behavior of the composites. On one hand, the matrix of the composites is easily microploughed due to lower hardness than the 10%Si composite. It leads to more wear. On the other hand, an increase in volume fraction of Al₂O₃p was found by increasing the Si content when Si content is higher than 10%. The increasing Al₂O₃p leads to a bad effect on the fracture toughness of MMCs especially with view to stress triaxiality [43] due to an decrease in the particle spacing and increase in Al₂O₃p/steel interface. This is mainly because the degree of Al₂O₃p clustering is expected to influence the wear performance by providing preferential sites for crack nucleation [16]. Thus, obvious interfacial cracks are present on the worn surface (see Fig. 9(d)). Subsequently, it leads to delamination of the oxidization layer. Therefore, the volume losses of the composites increase along with the increasing Si content when the Si content is higher than 10%.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This study investigated the effect of Si content added in the preforms on the wear performance of Al₂O₃p/steel composites fabricated by squeeze casting. The results are summarized as follows:

(1) The Si content in the preforms can strongly affect the microstructure and impact abrasive wear performance of Al₂O₃p/steel composites.

(2) The composite without Si adding contains only pearlite in the matrix, but those with Si adding contain both pearlite and ferrite.

(3) The composites with Si adding are less worn than the composite without Si adding. With the increase of Si content, the volume loss first decreases and then increases, reaches the minimum wear at 10% Si composite.

(4) The ferrite in the steel matrix of the 10%Si composite has the highest micro-hardness. However, the micro-hardness of the pearlite first increases and then decreases as the Si content increases, and reaches the peak value at 15%Si composite.

(5) With the increase of the added Si, the contact angles between steel and Al₂O₃p decreases.

(6) The wear mechanism of the composites is abrasive wear when the Si content is less than 10%, otherwise it is a mixed mode of abrasive and delamination wear. The wear behavior of the composites is controlled by a combination of the hardness of the metal matrix and the interfacial bonding strength.

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